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Joint forces: towards an integration of intellectual capital theory and the open innovation paradigm

Abstract

Intellectual capital (IC) is among the most long-lived topics in managerial literature. More recently, the emergence of the open innovation (OI) paradigm has encouraged the understanding that firms should collaborate with other organizations to leverage their own R&D capabilities. We propose that these two streams of managerial literature should join forces since the OI paradigm could be considered an approach to innovation with foundations in relational capital, facilitated by an appropriate level of human and structural capital. Surprisingly, few researchers attempted to put IC and OI into relation. Therefore, this paper has two main goals: providing a theoretical model that synoptically presents how IC and OI overlap and testing the theoretical model by analyzing how firms' IC affects OI-related performance. We study a sample of 3,744 Spanish firms from the PITEC dataset. We show that the three IC constructs positively affect OI performance. Relational and human capital show diminishing returns on OI performance.

Keywords intellectual capital; open innovation; innovation performance; human capital; relational capital; structural capital.

Joint forces: towards an integration of intellectual capital theory and open innovation paradigm

1. Introduction

In the past decade, a stream of managerial literature has developed around the open innovation (OI) paradigm (West, Salter, Vanhaverbeke, & Chesbrough, 2014), describing how firms could and should interact with external organizations to foster their own R&D investments. The rationale behind such paradigm lies in that interaction with other subjects is likely to reduce the risks embedded in pursuing innovation, while increasing the odds of success thanks to the partners' competencies (Belderbos, Faems, Leten, Van Looy, & Looy, 2010). Nevertheless, the OI paradigm also emphasizes the importance of the firm's own intangible assets (including knowledge, competency skills, intellectual property, etc.), which are considered complementary with respect to those drawn from external organizations. The existing literature on Intellectual Capital (IC) has shown interest in such intangible assets for decades, classifying them into three categories: human, structural, and relational capital. Human capital refers to all firm human resources and describes their cumulative tacit knowledge, skills and competences. Structural capital describes the explicit knowledge embedded in an organization and its corporate culture. Finally, relational capital represents the relations and knowledge exchanges with the organization's external stakeholders (Andriessen, 2004; Edvinsson & Malone, 1997; Sveiby, 1997).

Thus, the link between IC and OI is very marked, and the OI paradigm might be considered an approach to innovation, built upon relational capital, and simultaneously facilitated by an appropriate level of both human and structural capital. Indeed, one of

the OI cornerstones is absorptive capacity, a firm's ability to incorporate know-how, ideas, and technology from other organizations (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990). In fact, absorptive capacity is an intangible organizational asset in itself, determined by firm IC (Harison & Koski, 2010), since it derives from both human-resources competencies and the firm structural knowledge processes.

Despite much of the OI-related literature being fundamentally aimed at discussing the enhancement of innovation performance by both firm human and structural capital stocks (e.g. employee education, R&D investments, etc), leveraged by relational capital (e.g. type of innovation partners, intensity of the links with them, etc.), the respective OI-paradigm and IC-related research lines have seldom converged into a more enriching, multifaceted perspective. Indeed, in recent years, several studies have dwelt on the absence of a structured framework successfully bringing IC components and OI practices together (Chen, Zhao, & Wang, 2015; Michelino, Cammarano, Lamberti, & Caputo, 2014; Rogo, Cricelli, & Grimaldi, 2014). Such an absence has been considered a remarkable research gap (Macchi, Rizzo, & Ramaciotti, 2014).

IC has been considered a wealth-creating resource for organizations (e.g. Bini, Dainelli, & Giunta, 2016; Martin, 2004; Stewart, 1997), given its enhancement of innovation performance (Rogo et al., 2014). This article intends to promote the current understanding of IC-related effects by establishing a connection with the OI paradigm, therefore assuming the ability of IC to enhance OI successfulness. To this aim, this article puts forward a pioneering framework to demonstrate how the OI paradigm may actually build upon IC, and its ability to foster OI success in terms of product-innovation performance. Departing from the premise that successful OI performance is driven by human, structural, and relational capital, such framework has been tested through data

from 3,744 Spanish firms.

2. Theoretical background and hypotheses

2.1. Introducing the open innovation paradigm

According to the OI paradigm, purposeful firm interaction with external organizations leverages internal R&D effort, subsequently enhancing innovativeness. Indeed, outside the organizational boundaries, a wide range of ideas, competencies, and technologies may be incorporated to boost a company's competitive advantage. Consistently, many studies have demonstrated the benefits of OI in terms of innovation performance (West & Bogers, 2014).

Thus, firms must take up the challenge to enhance their collaborative skills and effectively gather knowledge, technology, and ideas from their partners. Such capability is usually referred to as absorptive capacity and has been studied in terms of openness to new ideas (Fey & Birkinshaw, 2005); knowledge-oriented responsiveness; practice-updating propensity upon receipt of new information (Jantunen, 2005); or the extent of external knowledge acquisition, assimilation, transformation, and exploitation (Jansen, Van Den Bosch, & Volberda, 2005). Therefore, absorptive capacity is a knowledge-based asset (Vega-Jurado, Gutiérrez-Gracia, & Fernández-de-Lucio, 2009; Xie, Wang, & Zeng, 2018; Xie, Zou, & Qi, 2018) with the ability to translate interorganizational knowledge acquisition into innovation (Xie, Wang, et al., 2018).

2.2. IC stocks as the cornerstone of open innovation

An analysis of the OI paradigm from an IC-theory oriented approach has led us to identify several insightful parallelisms.

A first and crucial element in OI lies in both the quality and quantity of innovation-

driven firm partnerships. Similarly, relational capital comprises both the density and effectivity of an organization's partner networks. Here, the OI paradigm differs from IC in its strong orientation toward innovation, fostered not only by the thus far accumulated amount of relational capital but also by its strategic employment to enhance internal R&D efforts.

A second element refers to the role played by human resources in inter-organizational collaborations. This depends on a firm's attitude towards externally developed ideas (du Chatenier, Verstegen, Biemans, Mulder, & Omta, 2010). Such an element is patently linked with human capital, as defined in the IC theory.

The third cornerstone of OI is the deployment of intellectual property not simply for defensive purposes, but also as a means for drawing financial returns from unused inventions (Chesbrough, West, & Vanhaverbeke, 2006). Again, In the IC theory, a firm intellectual property is a core element of the structural capital.

As observed by Michelino et al. (2014), most of the usual OI-associated metrics may be directly or indirectly related to IC. Such strong links between key elements of the OI paradigm and of the IC theory support our statement that OI depends on firm IC, as well as on the strategic use of such capital. Rogo et al. (2014) have been the first to emphasize the emerging need to identify how IC components foster OI practices. Nevertheless, with few exceptions, the respective OI and IC literature streams have rarely met.

Chen et al. (2015) have acknowledged the need to integrate IC and OI, and consequently proposed a re-interpretive framework for the three IC elements (human, structural, and relational capital), splitting IC into two dimensions: internal (i.e., the

focal organization's characteristics), and external (i.e., those of a different organization cooperating with it). Both branches are again divided into the traditional human, structural, and relational capital classifiers. However, some differences between internal and external constructs appear questionable. For example, while internal structural capital refers to “*the mechanism and structure of the company, including its information systems, databases, operation flows, and corporate culture*” (Chen et al., 2015, p. 6), external structural capital refers to “*the information systems, databases, operation flows, and corporate culture of the cooperative organisations*” (Chen et al., 2015, p. 7). In other words, according to the authors, the external organizations' IC is part of the focal firm's own IC. Although external subjects are likely to influence internal IC, we do not consider it wise to confuse IC internal and external stocks. Unlike the framework proposed by Chen et al (2015), we consider the OI paradigm as compatible with traditional IC theory, while agreeing on the urgent need to clarify how the two theories interact with each other. In the following sections, we will discuss how such interactions take place.

2.3. The effect of relational capital on open innovation success

According to OI, an increase in firm interaction with other organizations translates into a growing ability to gather external ideas, competencies, knowledge, technologies, and other intangible assets, which in turn offers better chances of innovation. This is in line with Allen's theory of technology transfer (1977), and with the resource-based view (Wernerfelt, 1984), since firms need to combine their own tangible and intangible resources with those owned by other organizations (Vanhaverbeke & Cloudt, 2006). However beneficial partner collaboration may be to enhance firm performance, an excessive number of active collaborations or the continuous resort to different categories of partners may be detrimental, due to the over-search and over-

collaboration phenomena (Duysters & Lokshin, 2011; Greco, Grimaldi, & Cricelli, 2016; Laursen & Salter, 2006). Therefore, our first hypothesis is formulated as follows:

Hypothesis 1. Relational capital is curvilinearly (taking an inverted U-shape) related to a firm's ability to collaboratively develop product innovations with external subjects.

2.4. The effect of human and structural capital on open innovation success

Both individual resources (human capital) and organizational processes and intellectual property (structural capital) are likely to nurture firm capability for external knowledge acquisition, assimilation, transformation, and exploitation (Jansen et al., 2005; Xie, Zou, et al., 2018). Several studies have explicitly analyzed the moderating effect of human and structural capital on collaborative innovation success. Indeed, Foss et al. (2010) have demonstrated that several organizational practices are critical to foster customer collaboration-related innovation performance. Similarly, according to Cabello-Medina et al. (2011), human capital has a direct and positive effect on firm innovativeness, additionally enhanced by social capital and human resources management practices. In turn, Lazzarotti et al. (2015) contend that both the organizational and social antecedents of absorptive capacity act as strong mediators in the relationship between openness and performance. In another article (2016), the same authors underscore the major role of certain managerial mechanisms (potentially considered structural capital) in the effect of scientific-partner collaboration on innovation performance.

Notably, the aforementioned intangible assets leveraging OI performance may be considered absorptive capacity enablers in terms of both human and structural capital, given their accelerating potential in a context of external-knowledge assimilation,

helping firms to commercialize collaboration outcomes (Fabrizio, 2009). Thus, we propose both human and structural capital as the anchor of absorptive capacity, with a subsequent, intensifying role in OI success. Should this reasoning be extrapolated to relational capital, the afore-described relationship may be hypothesized to entail diminishing returns since the companies achieving a certain level of strongly qualified human capital, or a high stock of internal knowledge, are less focused on collaboration projects and may prioritize internal innovation initiatives.

Hypothesis 2. Human capital is curvilinearly (taking an inverted U-shape) related to a firm's ability to collaboratively develop product innovations with external subjects.

Hypothesis 3. Structural capital is curvilinearly (taking an inverted U-shape) related to a firm's ability to collaboratively develop product innovations with external subjects.

2.5. Human, structural, and relational capital joint effect on OI performance

According to the existing literature, IC components are likely to affect one another. In one of the first studies of this nature, Bontis (1998) has found that human capital positively influences both structural and customer capital (an early interpretation of relational capital restricted to customer relations). In turn, Sveiby (2001) has discussed how individual competence, internal and external structure (respective forms of structural and relational capital) influence one another by virtue of knowledge transfer. Starovic and Marr (2003) have also considered the reciprocal influences among several IC components, particularly describing the interdependence between human and structural capital, but also emphasizing the effect of corporate culture on stakeholder relationships. Ritala et al. (2009) have enumerated the drivers of a firm's ability to build and manage innovation networks, identifying both organizational- and individual-level

determinants. Similarly, Jolink and Dankbaar (2010) have demonstrated the role of several human resources-related, organizational and psychological factors in creating a fostering climate for inter-organizational collaborations. The positive effect of structural and human capital on relational capital is also supported by Podmetina et al. (2013), while Kianto et al. (2017) have observed that human capital improves innovation performance by enhancing structural and relational capital.

Simultaneously, relational capital enriches both human and structural capital by influencing human resources management, improving procedures, etc. Starovic and Marr (2003) have advanced the proposal that stakeholder relationships may bear a positive effect on human capital. Similarly, Petroni et al. (2012) have suggested that OI-paradigm adoption influences the organization of internal R&D structures and human resources. In this vein, and regarding value drivers, Cricelli et al. (2013) have indicated that knowledge and competence (both human capital components), and intellectual property and technology (structural capital elements) may affect (and be affected by) other value drivers such as investor-, customer-, and partner and supplier-relations. Further, it is Užienė's position (2015) that an interorganizational knowledge flow increase is likely to influence human capital, while Villasalero (2014) states that, thanks to their relationships with universities and other organizations, firms located within science parks are subject to a more intense development of human resources, key technologies, innovation-related knowledge, and solid reputation.

Overall, research in this field suggests the existence of interdependencies among the different IC components. Therefore, in addition to the already-hypothesized, direct and individual effect on OI performance, a case may also be made for a joint one.

Hp 4.a Human and structural capital jointly improve a firm's chances to collaboratively develop product innovations with external subjects.

Hp 4.b Human and relational capital jointly improve a firm's chances to collaboratively develop product innovations with external subjects.

Hp 4.c Structural and relational capital jointly improve a firm's chances to collaboratively develop product innovations with external subjects.

2.6. An OI/IC integrative framework

Based on the literature reviewed so far, Figure 1 graphically illustrates the relationship between OI and IC, describing the fundamental components of the IC theory, the OI paradigm and the interactions mentioned above. The figure also integrates the hypotheses formulated in previous subsections.

In our proposed framework, relational capital is considered both an integrating part of IC (defined by black border line), and a positively-influencing cornerstone of the OI paradigm (grey-highlighted). Absorptive capacity comprises both human and structural capital, which are expected to bear an impact on OI success. As hypothesized in Section 2.5, all three IC components reinforce one another.

Figure 1. Interplay between the IC framework and the OI paradigm.

3. Methodology

Our hypotheses have been tested through the analysis of a manufacturing-firm, longitudinal sample. This longitudinal feature has enabled to support the causal relationships drawn between the variables. All sample-, variable-, and model-related details are presented hereafter.

Figure 2 summarizes the statistical procedure followed in this paper. Firstly, we have created and validated the latent constructs to measure structural, human, and relational capital through factor analysis. Secondly, a two-step logit model has been estimated for the purpose of examining the effect of each type of capital on OI success. An in-depth depiction of the data, variables and models in this process will be provided in the following sections.

Figure 2. Steps for statistical analysis of our data

3.1. Data and variables

Our dataset has been retrieved from the Spanish Survey of Technological Innovation (PITEC), one of the most comprehensive surveys on innovation in Spain (Garcia Martinez, Zouaghi, & Sanchez Garcia, 2017). The PITEC provides highly-compatible panel data from firm sampling across different waves, which allows the use of lagged explanatory variables for analytical purposes (Belderbos, Gilsing, & Lokshin, 2012). Such a framework has been tested on a sample collected in a period comprised between 2008 and 2015. Our final compilation contains data from 3,744 firms, among which 3,226 are

SMEs (under 250 employees) and 653, large firms¹ and a total of 13,509 observations.

The hypotheses formulated in this paper are therefore put to test by studying the effect of three IC independent latent constructs (*HumanCapital*, *StructuralCapital*, and *RelationalCapital*) on a dependent binary variable measuring OI performance in terms of new product development (*OIsuccess*). *OIsuccess* takes a value of 1 upon product innovation through collaboration with other organizations in the past two years; and 0, if otherwise (Gómez, Salazar, & Vargas, 2016).

The three latent constructs used to assess IC are defined as follows:

Following Teixeira and Tavares-Lehman (2014), and Garcia Martinez et al. (2017), *HumanCapital* is assessed through the percentage of top-skilled, R&D human resources— i.e., research and technical staff members (*QualifiedHR*), and the number of R&D employees with tertiary education or higher (*RDskills*).

StructuralCapital is captured by three variables: *IProperty*, *OrgInnovation*, and *CommInnovation*. *IProperty* ranges between 0 and 4 depending on the number of methods used by a firm to protect intellectual property: patents, utility models, brands, and copyright (Martinez-Senra, Quintas, Sartal, & Vazquez, 2015). *OrgInnovation* and *CommInnovation* account for organizational and commercialization innovation, respectively. *OrgInnovation* is a dummy variable which scores 1 upon firm innovation in both work-organizational and processual practices, in the means of better-distributing responsibilities and decision-making tasks. On its part, *CommInnovation* takes a value of 1 upon firm innovation in commercialization.

¹ The current sum exceeds 3, 744 since some firms have undergone transformation during the period of study.

RelationalCapital is assessed through a six-item set describing all potential partnership modalities—customers, suppliers, competitors, same-enterprise-group entities, universities or others—, and four geographical locations—Spain, EU, USA, or others. We have therefore created six cooperation variables (one for each partnership modality), taking values from 0 to 4, depending on each partner's involved number of geographical locations.

Subsequently, the three latent variables obtained have been subjected to a two-year lag in order to avoid endogeneity issues (since, for instance, successful open innovation may increase the chances to obtain partner cooperation for innovation purposes, which entails a correlational growth of relational capital) and to consider that the independent variables may need time to affect innovation outcomes since the innovation process needs time to be performed.

We use two typical control variables in the analysis of innovation: firm size and firm age (Chandy & Tellis, 2000; Garcia Martinez et al., 2017). Firm size is measured as the logarithmic transformation of the total number of employees (*lnSize*), and firm age is calculated as the logarithm of the number of years since the firm foundation (*lnAge*). Special attention has been paid to the incidence of enterprise-group firms (*group*), as well as to their export propensity (*export*), measured by the turnover figures scored in foreign markets. In order to account for specific, sector- and time-related effects, our model considers a set of 12 dummy industry labels and year dummies representing the eight waves of the survey included in the sample. We have also surveyed R&D intensity, *lnR&Dintensity* (calculated as the logarithm of internal R&D expenditures over sales), and innovativeness probability (*pr_innovation*), representing firm-innovativeness potential, which is calculated through a first-stage logit regression.

Three binary control variables have equally been used only in the first-stage regression to estimate *pr_innovation*. Such variables reflect the existence (or absence) of innovation obstacles: *cost_obs*, referring to excessively high innovation costs; *dominating_obs*, representing the existence of market-dominating firms; and *demand_obs*, illustrating the lack of innovation demand.

Table 1 summarizes the variables considered in our study.

TABLE 1 SHOULD BE PLACED HERE

3.2. Model

Although our study focuses on the effect of IC on firm OI performance, restricting the analysis to innovative firms might entail a selection bias. To address it, a two-part logit model has been implemented (Cameron & Trivedi, 2005; De Marchi, 2012; Vega-Jurado et al., 2009). The suitability of such method has been estimated superior to that of the Heckman selection model since the main model's dependent variable is of binary, rather than continuous, nature (Haas & Hansen, 2005).

In the first stage, a selection model has been devised on the basis of the observations at our disposal (i.e. including both innovative and non-innovative firms). Similarly to De Marchi 's study (2012), the *lnSize*, *group*, *cost_obs*, *dominating_obs*, *demand_obs*, and time and industry dummy variables have been considered in the model. This selection model has therefore enabled the estimation of firm-innovation probability (*pr_innovation*).

The independent variables (*HumanCapital*, *StructuralCapital*, and *RelationalCapital*) have been calculated from the results of an exploratory factor analysis. In this regard, our first step has been to examine the complex, latent variables in terms of internal consistency, reliability, and construct validity (MacKenzie, Podsakoff, & Jarvis, 2005).

To test our hypotheses while avoiding selection bias, second-stage models have been later deployed using the dependent variable *OIsuccess*, thus omitting all non-innovative firms, yet including the independent variables, *pr_innovation*, and the aforementioned control variables.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Exploratory factor analysis

To test construct validity for the *HumanCapital*, *StructuralCapital*, and *RelationalCapital* variables a factor analysis has been applied to all IC variables discussed in subsection 3.1, using the principal components as an extraction method with an eigenvalue exceeding 1, and a Varimax rotation method. In line with our expectations, the results (see Table 2) indicate the existence of three factors, the relationship of each variable with the underlying factor expressed by factor loadings. Factor 1 defines *RelationalCapital* since it comprises all cooperation-related variables. Factor 2, grouping *QualifiedHR* and *RDskills*, consequently describes *HumanCapital*; and Factor 3 represents *StructuralCapital*, composed by the variables *IProperty*, *OrgInnovation*, and *CommInnovation*.

TABLE 2 SHOULD BE PLACED HERE

The reliability of all three variables is measured through the Cronbach alpha. The resulting values (0.818 for *RelationalCapital*; 0.846 for *HumanCapital*; and 0.529 for *StructuralCapital*) exceed the generally accepted, early-stage research threshold, established at 0.5 (Nunnally, 1967), which therefore confirms their acceptability. Moreover, the general estimators Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO test) have scored a value of 0.794, which is above the 0.7 threshold for factor-analysis quality, and therefore suitable

(Bartlett, 1950). On its part, the variance explained by factor analysis amounts to 59.9%, which exceeds the 52% threshold suggested by Henson and Roberts (2006).

4.2. Regression results

Table 3 includes the results of our second-stage logit models². Model 1 includes all firms in the sample. In the means of providing further elements for analysis, while testing cross-industry result robustness, regression has been run on two sample subsets, comprising high-tech (Model 2) and low-tech firms (Model 3) respectively. The resulting impact may be quantified through coefficient exponentiation. For instance, if the *RelationalCapital* coefficient is exponentiated in Model 1, it may be stated that, upon one-standard deviation growth in *RelationalCapital*, the odds for *OIsuccess* increase by a factor of $e^{0.872}=2.392$ (factors normalized to have mean 0 and standard deviation 1; see Stata Manual, StataCorp, 2013). Nevertheless, the presence of both quadratic and interaction terms makes coefficient interpretation less straightforward. Additionally, the nature of our independent-factor variables renders it less interesting to quantify the impact of a construct on *OIsuccess*. Instead, the main goal of this paper is to verify whether such impact exists, as well as its sign.

TABLE 3 SHOULD BE PLACED HERE

Model 1 demonstrates a positive and statistically significant effect of *RelationalCapital* on *OIsuccess*. Indeed, partnership geographical and organizational diversity is likely to enhance OI success as a result of multiple complementarities and synergies (Belderbos et al., 2012). Besides, the partners' geographical variability facilitates the adaptation of existing products to local requirements such as technical

² First-part regression results are not provided in this paper for the purpose of brevity, but they are available from authors upon request.

standards, market regulations, and customer preferences (Van Beers & Zand, 2014).

As expected, the *RelationalCapital* squared term displays a negative and statistically significant coefficient, confirming a positive contribution of *RelationalCapital* to *OIsuccess* until a certain maximum extent, where it starts to decrease. This inverted U shape is confirmed by Lind & Mehlum's test (2010). Therefore, Model 1 supports Hypothesis 1 (a curvilinear relationship between *RelationalCapital* and *OIsuccess*, taking an inverted U-shape), and is aligned with previous studies, suggesting the negative effect of over-collaboration on innovation performance (Duysters & Lokshin, 2011; Greco et al., 2016; Laursen & Salter, 2006).

The positive and statistically significant coefficient of *HumanCapital* indicates that hiring more qualified staff increases OI success, while the negative and statistically significant coefficient of the squared *HumanCapital* term suggests diminishing returns. However, Lind and Melhum's test demonstrates that the *HumanCapital/OIsuccess* relationship does not take an inverted U-shape. Therefore, Hypothesis 2, proposing a curvilinear, inverted U-shape relationship between *HumanCapital* and *OIsuccess* is only partially supported. Such result is particularly interesting since it underscores that, while moderately diminishing returns correlate to an increase in staff qualifications, there is no evidence of a turning point from which additional qualifications may be detrimental. In other words, when it comes to human capital, there is no "too much".

On another front, the *StructuralCapital* coefficient is positive and significant, although its magnitude suggests a comparatively lower impact than that of both *HumanCapital* and *RelationalCapital*, besides its squared term's lack of statistical significance. Therefore, the resulting relationship is not subject to diminishing returns, which definitely refutes

Hypothesis 3 (a curvilinear, inverted U-shape relationship between structural capital and OI success). Accordingly, managers should nurture their firms' structural capital (i.e. enhance their intellectual property and promote organizational improvements).

Our Hypotheses 4.a, 4.b, and 4.c have been built upon the prospection of a positive, joint IC-component effect on OI success, due to their mutual-reinforcement ability. Contrary to our expectations, most of the interaction-effect coefficients lacked statistical significance, while sufficient statistical evidence has been gathered of a negative – albeit small in magnitude - interaction term between *HumanCapital* and *RelationalCapital*. This contrasts our Hypothesis 4.b, an overall explanation for which may reside in the Not-Invented-Here syndrome, referring to the acceptance of elsewhere-developed ideas, technology or approaches upon tacit, internal human resources suspicion, or even explicit opposition (Katz & Allen, 1982). This is actually coincident with a study by Srivastava et al. (2015), demonstrating the reversing potential of high technological capabilities on the positive effect of alliances. Therefore, despite the ability of qualified human resources to both leverage and encourage the success of internal R&D and OI, they may also bear a hampering effect on some collaborative practices. However, the *HumanCapital*RelationalCapital* interaction term seems well counterbalanced by the positive coefficients of *HumanCapital* and *RelationalCapital*. Overall, firms should implement actions to facilitate the acceptance of know-how technologies coming from external sources (Salge, Farchi, Barrett, & Dopson, 2013). The refutation of Hypotheses 4.a, 4.b, and 4.c should be taken with caution since a reinforcing effect could take place under specific circumstances, or require longer time-lags to acquire significance.

Among the control variables discussed, *lnR&Dintensity* and *group* have displayed a considerable effect on *OIsuccess*, in contrast with *lnSize*, *lnAge*, and *exports*. The

pr_innovation coefficient is statistically significant, supporting our methodological choices to address the selection bias issue.

On a separate issue, the analysis of the high-tech and low-tech sample subsets has returned interesting additional insights. Indeed, while *RelationalCapital* displays a sustained significance as an *Olsuccess* driver in both cases, no curvilinearity can be spotted in the case of high-tech firms, whereas an inverted U-shape relationship may be observed in the low-tech subsample. We, therefore, may underscore the need of firms in innovative and turbulent sectors to constantly expand their partner network for sustained competitiveness, and a subsequent urge to deploy managing practices avoiding diminishing or even negative returns. In contrast, low-tech firms may have grown less accustomed to multiple partnerships, thus finding a reduced partnership network more profitable. Among the rest of IC components, one clearly observable pattern is high-tech-firm reliance on *StructuralCapital*, rather than on *HumanCapital*, for *Olsuccess* enhancement, without experiencing diminishing returns while entailing further positive effect of the interaction term between *StructuralCapital* and *RelationalCapital*.

By contrast, low-tech firms' preferred resource for *Olsuccess* is *HumanCapital*, rather than on *StructuralCapital*, despite the relationship between *HumanCapital* and *Olsuccess* being curvilinear, represented by an inverted U-shape.

Such discrepancy could be attributed to need among high-tech firms to systemize their know-how and protect their intellectual property to surpass their competitors, whereas low-tech firms may draw more benefits from the involvement of a skilled, reasonably-sized human-resources team. Industry-specific propensity to protect

intellectual property may also play a relevant role in explaining the difference between high-tech and low-tech firms with respect to the *StructuralCapital* variable since the latter are less accustomed to protecting their intellectual property (Heidenreich, 2009).

Finally, additional models have been run (not displayed here for brevity) by segmenting model 2 and model 3 according to firm size (SMEs vs large firms). The results obtained are quite unexpected in the two low-tech models, where SME *OIsuccess* is positively driven by *StructuralCapital* and *HumanCapital*, while large firms *OIsuccess* is positively driven by *RelationalCapital* (all relationships subject to diminishing returns).

5. Conclusions

This article has introduced a theoretical framework aimed at exploring the relationship between the IC theory and the OI paradigm. It has been contended that OI has its foundations in the three traditional IC components, human, structural, and relational capital, the first two being absorptive-capacity enablers. On the grounds of our literature review, several hypotheses have been formulated to discern how human, structural, and relational capital enhance OI success. As a result, while a curvilinear inverted U-shape relationship has been demonstrated between relational capital and OI success, the relationship between human capital and OI success is only subject to diminishing returns. Instead, no diminishing returns stem from the positive relationship between structural capital and OI success. Additionally, high-tech and low-tech firms have been proven to display different patterns in terms of our research focus. In high-tech firms, no diminishing returns are involved in the positive effect of relational and structural capital on OI success, whereas the same effect in low-tech firms takes an inverted U-shape. Further peculiarities emerge when comparing SMEs and large firms

operating in similarly innovative sectors.

From a theoretical perspective, our results support the framework defined in this article, drawing a solid connection between IC and OI, with a strong emphasis on the positive role of the three IC components as enhancers of OI-related innovation. Thus, there certainly is room for cross-fertilization between the two popular streams of managerial literature. The relationships observed between human and structural capital and OI success allow a better understanding of the role played by absorptive capacity in regard to OI, encouraging future research on the topic. Consequently, future studies should further analyze the multiple intersections among the three IC components, given the heterogeneity of the results returned by this study, partially contradicting the hypothesized relationships among them.

From a managerial perspective, this article suggests that firms pursuing OI success should develop relational capital to benefit from cross-organizational synergies and complementarities. This is in line with the recommendations advanced by Martinez et al. (2017) in order to improve innovation performance. However, managers should also become increasingly aware of the risks involved in excessive relational capital reliance, which can result in phenomena such as over-collaboration and over-searching. Furthermore, managers should acknowledge that the three IC dimensions studied in this article can enhance firm innovation capability, with a consequent, leveraging effect on OI. Thus, together with the often-studied importance of relational capital, all managerial practices pursuing OI performance should adopt an integrated approach considering human and structural capital as enabling OI success-related.

Our article furthermore has indirect social implications, since a more effective

innovation-process management by intersecting OI and IC will ultimately result in accelerated and enhanced innovation, which is likely to translate into social progress and improved individual-need satisfaction.

This paper has some limitations. Firstly, our binary dependent variable does not measure the intensity of OI success. Future studies may resort to more sophisticated dependent variables to improve our understanding of the relationship between IC and OI. We encourage further studies to extend our analysis to cross-national datasets in the means of testing the robustness of our exploratory results, as well as to further explore the multiple firm-, size-, and sector-innovativeness related differences. Further research could also explore the potential existence of an optimal balance between the IC components to enhance OI success. Finally, given the factorial nature of our IC variables, no discussion is provided as to how a certain increase in their values may alter OI success probability. Future research is encouraged to explore how the variables composing the three IC factors influence OI success and provide insightful information to practitioners.

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Tables

Var. Type	LC	La g	Variables	Description	Obs	Me an	St.D v	Mi n	Ma x
Dependent (observed)		<i>t</i>	<i>OIsuccess</i>	Dummy variable of OI product success: It takes 1 if the firm obtains product innovation from OI; 0, otherwise.	13'509	0.20	0.40	0	1
Latent	C a p i t a l	<i>H u n a n a t-2</i>	<i>Qualified HR</i>	Percentage of R&D staff with tertiary education/R&D staff	13'509	37.5	33.72	0	100
		<i>p i t a l t-2</i>	<i>RDskills</i>	Percentage of top skilled R&D workers (technicians, researchers)/R&D staff	13'509	63.7	39.15	0	100
		<i>S t r c t u r a l t-2</i>	<i>IProperty</i>	Ranges between 0-4, depending on the number of intellectual property methods used: patents, utility models, copyrights, brands.	13'509	0.52	0.84	0	4
		<i>u t i l i z a t i o n t-2</i>	<i>OrgInnovation</i>	Takes value 1 if the firm introduced organizational innovations; 0 otherwise	13'509	0.53	0.50	0	1
		<i>C a p i t a l t-2</i>	<i>CommInnovation</i>	Takes value 1 if the firm introduced commercialization innovations; 0 otherwise	13'509	0.46	0.50	0	1
		<i>R e l a t i o n a l t-2</i>	<i>Coopfirm</i>	Captures cooperation inside the firm or group. Takes values between 0-4 depending on the number of locations of partners: Spain, EU, USA or others.	13'509	0.23	0.57	0	4
		<i>i n n o n a l t-2</i>	<i>Coopcust</i>	Captures cooperation with customers. Takes values between 0-4 depending on the number of locations of partners: Spain, EU, USA or others.	13'509	0.26	0.66	0	4
		<i>C a p i t a l t-2</i>	<i>Coopsup</i>	Captures cooperation with suppliers. Takes values between 0-4 depending on the number of locations of partners, Spain, EU, USA or others.	13'509	0.26	0.57	0	4

Var. Type	LC	La g	Variables	Description	Obs	Me an	St.D v	Mi n	Ma x
Control (observed)	<i>i</i>	<i>t-2</i>	<i>Coopcomp</i>	Captures cooperation with competitors. Takes values between 0-4 depending on the number of locations of partners, Spain, EU, USA or others.	13'509	0.11	0.39	0	4
		<i>t-2</i>	<i>Coopuniv</i>	Captures cooperation with universities. Takes values between 0-4 depending on the number of locations of partners, Spain, EU, USA or others.	13'509	0.20	0.48	0	4
		<i>t-2</i>	<i>Coopothers</i>	Captures cooperation with others (public research institutes, technological centers, commercial labs). Takes values between 0-4 depending on the number of locations of partners, Spain, EU, USA or others.	13'509	0.29	0.54	0	4
		<i>t</i>	<i>lnSize</i>	Logarithm of the number of employees	37,439	3.98	1.415	0	9.23
		<i>t</i>	<i>lnAge</i>	Years since the foundation of the firm	13'509	3.37	0.55	1.1	5.20
		<i>t</i>	<i>lnR&Dintensity</i>	Logarithm of one plus Internal R&D expenditures/sales	13'509	0.03	0.08	0	1.62
		<i>t</i>	<i>group</i>	Dummy variable: it takes 1 if the firm pertains to the same group of companies; 0, otherwise.	37,439	0.41	0.493	0	1
	First stage-regression	<i>t</i>	<i>export</i>	Rate of exports over sales (%)	13'509	14.4	19.93	0	100
		<i>t</i>	<i>innprod</i>	Dummy variable: it takes 1 if the firm has perform product innovation; 0 otherwise.	37,439	0.54	0.498	0	1
		<i>t</i>	<i>cost_obs</i>	Obstacle to innovate: too high innovation costs	37,439	2.15	1.075	1	4
<i>t</i>		<i>dominating_obs</i>	Obstacle to innovate: presence of firms dominating the market	37,439	2.53	1.043	1	4	
	<i>t</i>	<i>demand_obs</i>	Obstacle to innovate: lack of demand for innovation	37,439	3.20	0.928	1	4	

Table 1. Variables of the study

Table 2 Exploratory Factor analysis of IC.

Items	Factors		
	1	2	3
<i>QualifiedHR</i>		0.911	0.151
<i>RDskills</i>	0.153	0.890	0.223
<i>OrgInnovation</i>	0.143	0.086	0.775
<i>CommInnovation</i>	0.055	0.081	0.835
<i>IProperty</i>	0.134	0.233	0.500
<i>Coopfirm</i>	0.748	0.053	0.079
<i>Coopcust</i>	0.738	0.085	0.082
<i>Coopsup</i>	0.775	0.052	0.120
<i>Coopcomp</i>	0.602	0.050	0.054
<i>Coopuniv</i>	0.691	0.166	0.111
<i>Coopothers</i>	0.707	0.186	0.147
Percentage of the explained variance (%)	0.285	0.160	0.153
Percentage Accumulated from variance (%)	0.285	0.446	0.599
Cronbach Alpha (%)	0.818	0.846	0.529

Extraction Method: Principal Components; RotationMethod: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization; 4 iterations

Table3. Second-stage regression results on *OIsuccess* dependent variable.

	Model1		Model2		Model3	
	All firms		High-tech		Low-tech	
	Coef.	Std.Err.	Coef.	Std.Err.	Coef.	Std.Err.
<i>StructuralCapital</i>	0.135**	0.058	0.345* *	0.164	0.128	0.112
<i>HumanCapital</i>	0.256***	0.062	0.075	0.204	0.448***	0.126
<i>RelationalCapital</i>	0.872***	0.061	0.481* *	0.227	1.048***	0.118
<i>StructuralCapital</i> ²	0.003	0.037	0.019	0.122	0.013	0.073
<i>HumanCapital</i> ²	-0.091**	0.045	-0.156	0.176	-0.182*** †	0.066
<i>RelationalCapital</i> ²	-0.097*** †	0.012	-0.058	0.063	-0.140*** †	0.025
<i>StructuralCapital*</i> <i>HumanCapital</i>	0.008	0.042	-0.262	0.171	-0.070	0.073
<i>StructuralCapital*</i> <i>RelationalCapital</i>	-0.044	0.028	0.209*	0.126	-0.081*	0.047
<i>HumanCapital*</i> <i>RelationalCapital</i>	-0.098**	0.030	0.086	0.219	-0.062	0.053
<i>pr_innovation</i>	0.483***	0.095	0.598*	0.344	0.256	0.174
<i>lnR&Dintensity</i>	1.580***	0.536	1.170	0.948	5.004***	1.521
<i>lnsize</i>	-0.132	0.092	-0.578	0.368	-0.002	0.199
<i>lnage</i>	-0.069	0.099	0.206	0.317	0.057	0.180
<i>group</i>	0.360***	0.113	1.413* **	0.439	0.195	0.219
<i>export</i>	0.003	0.002	0.008	0.006	0.003	0.005
<i>_cons</i>	-3.177***	0.455	- 3.807*	1.348	-3.491***	0.915

**

lnsig2u

_cons	1.391***	0.074	1.522* **	0.226	1.274***	0.148
N.observations	13509		1482		3487	
N.firms	3744		400		1041	
Loglik.	-5060		-562		-1308	
Chi-squared	908		124.8		226.7	

*Notes: All models include time and industry dummies; *p<0.10. **p<0.05. ***p<0.01; †Lind and Melhum test statistically significant.*